

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		22/11/2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Hou et al.	
Country of origin		Korea	
Publication year		2016	
Title of article		Early individualised manipulative rehabilitation following lumbar open laser microdiscectomy improves early post-operative functional disability: A randomized, controlled pilot study	
Title of journal		Journal of Back and Musculoskeletal Rehabilitation	
Volume 29	Issue	Pages 23-29	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial (pilot study)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, abstract, p. 24
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Patients who were undergoing lumbar discectomy.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 24
Types of intervention	Early individualised manipulative rehabilitation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, p. abstract, p. 25-26
Types of comparison	Active control group	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Abstract, p. 24-25
Types of outcome measures	Primary disability and pain, and secondary outcomes measures were quality of life and use of medication using self-reported	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 25

questionnaires.				
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To evaluate the feasibility of using early individualised manipulative rehabilitation whether the early post-operative disability and residual pain after lumbar open laser microdiscectomy can be improved, compared with active control care	Abstract, p. 24
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Randomised controlled pilot trial	p. 24
Start date	Not reported	
End date	Not reported	
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear Not available	

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	This study was conducted in the setting of a rehabilitation centre at a specialised hospital for spinal surgery.	p. 24
Inclusion criteria	We recruited 59 eligible patients 25–69 years old who were undergoing lumbar discectomy after screening and individual interview, which were performed by research surgeons.	p. 24
Exclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria were patients with any spinal deformity, planned revision surgery, or a serious systemic medical condition including diabetic neuropathy, cancer, and cardiovascular disease. We also excluded patients with pregnancy or mental illness precluding any intervention.	p. 24
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	p. 24

Intervention group

Intervention Group 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name		
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	14 Mean age = 45.7	p. 25 Fig. 1 p. 26 Table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	The patients allocated to OMT rehabilitation visited the hospital for baseline measurement and to receive the intervention between 2 and 3 weeks after surgery (post-operative days 15.4 ± 3.4 , mean \pm standard deviation (SD)). The OMT rehabilitation consisted of eight individualised sessions for four weeks within the treatment protocol (each session for 30 minutes long twice weekly). At each visit for the intervention, the patients were individually assessed and treated by the same practitioner who was allocated to the study during the entire sessions. All assessments and treatment processes were documented and reviewed by the surgeons and research osteopath allocated to the study. The practitioner chose and used a combination of the techniques in the standardised OMT rehabilitation protocol after an individual physical assessment. Although the techniques are standardized, the intensity and sequence of the treatment were individualised to each patient's tolerance level and the post-operative conditions at each visit. Spinal manipulation directly applied to the lumbar segments was not allowed. The structures and areas where the techniques were applied are associated with low back pain and functional disability of the lumbar spine. Patients allocated to the active control group visited the hospital for baseline measurement between 2 and 3 weeks after surgery (post-operative days 14.1 ± 1.1 , mean \pm SD).	p. 24-25

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Active control group	p. 24-27
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	7 Mean age control group = 54.9	p. 25 Fig. 1 p. 25 Fig. 1

Description (<i>include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components</i>)	Each patient in the control group received a home exercise booklet with verbal instruction and performed the home exercise programme for four weeks. The home exercise included trunk rotation in standing position by putting hands on the pelvis; trunk flexion with the flexed legs while lying supine. The active home exercise was recommended to perform twice a week for four weeks, each for half an hour.	p. 25
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Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	Roland-Morris disability questionnaire (RDQ)	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Disability Favors intervention	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	VAS	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Pain in low back and legs No difference	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	The physical component score (PCS) of the 36-item ShortForm (SF)	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Quality of Life Favors intervention	p. 25, p. 27 Table 2

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Medication use	p. 27 Table 2
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	(weekly)	p. 27 Table 2

Follow up

Follow up	4 weeks	Abstract, p. 25
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	This pilot study supports the feasibility of a future definitive randomised control trial and indicates this type of rehabilitation may be an important option for post-operative management after spinal surgery.	Abstract, p. 28

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>